

A PFHS (Precipitation from Homogeneous Solutions) Method for the Gravimetric Estimation of Gallium(III) and Indium(III)

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IN earlier communications¹⁻³ from this laboratory, benzoic acid and its derivatives have been successfully used for the gravimetric estimations of gallium(III) and indium(III). During recent years the homogeneous precipitation of metal ions by the addition of a suitable buffer solution of pH just sufficient to precipitate the required hydroxide produces an easily filtrable precipitate and the new technique of PFHS has since been developed and utilized for the estimation of aluminium⁴. The present communication deals with the modifications of the methods reported earlier by developing PFHS method for the gravimetric estimations of Ga(III) and In(III).

Experimental

Stock solutions of gallium(III) and indium(III) were prepared and standardised as described earlier¹⁻³.

Precipitating reagent: A buffer solution of pH 4.25 was prepared by dissolving 4.5 g of ammonium chloride, 5 g of benzoic acid and 15 g of ammonium benzoate in 2 litre of deionised water.

Procedure: Aliquot quantities of gallium(III) or indium(III) chloride solutions were taken, diluted to 50 ml and neutralized with dilute aqueous ammonia till a faint permanent cloudiness was observed which was removed by a careful dropwise addition of dilute hydrochloric acid. 30 ml of benzoate buffer solution was added to this clear solution which was then boiled for 2 min and allowed to stand for 40 min on a water bath when a white granular precipitate gradually settled down. The precipitate was filtered through a quantitative fluted filter paper (Whatman No. 44), washed with 2% ammonium benzoate solution, dried at 110°, ignited to M₂O₃ (M = Ga³⁺ or In³⁺), cooled and weighed.

Though a large number of experiments had been done to find the optimum conditions for complete precipitation viz., the effect of pH, time for digestion etc., yet for the sake of brevity the results obtained for the estimation of gallium(III) and indium(III) by this modified method at pH 4.5 only are discussed.

The standard deviation σ_e and standard error σ_m have been evaluated for a set of eight identical samples using the formulae

$$\sigma_e = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x_1)^2 - \sum_n(\bar{x})^2}{(n-1)}} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_m = \frac{\sigma_e}{n}$$

and are given in Table I. The low values of σ_m depict that the developed PFHS methods for the

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estimation of these metals are certainly better than the ordinary precipitation method.

TABLE I—GRAVIMETRIC ESTIMATION OF Ga³⁺ AND In³⁺, BY (A) PFHS METHOD AND (B) BASIC BENZOATE METHOD

Ga₂O₃ taken = 112.60 mg; In₂O₃ taken = 98.40 mg.

S.No.	Parameter evaluated	Gallium(III)		Indium(III)	
		Method A	Method B	Method A	Method B
1.	Average value for M ₂ O ₃ mgs for eight samples ($\bar{x}$)	112.55	112.38	98.42	98.26
2.	Standard deviation σ_e	3.614	4.277	3.420	6.655
3.	Standard error σ_m	0.452	0.535	0.427	0.832

The new procedures were further tested for the estimation of these metals in presence of many common foreign ions and it is possible to estimate Ga³⁺ and In³⁺ in presence of excess of Na⁺ and NH₄⁺ and equivalent amounts of Ca²⁺, Zn²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cd²⁺ and Mn²⁺ ions which are not precipitated under these conditions. However, a small fraction Co²⁺, Be²⁺ and Fe²⁺ gets co-precipitated in the first precipitation which is overcome by dissolving the precipitate in dilute hydrochloric acid and the subsequent reprecipitation of Ga³⁺ and In³⁺ by the usual procedure and thus removing adsorbed ions.

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Studies on Lebbekanin E, A New Saponin from *Albizzia lebbek* Benth.

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ALBIZZIA lebbek Benth. commonly known as "Siris" belongs to the family Leguminosae. Varshney *et al.*¹⁻⁴ have studied the various parts of this tree and isolated four new saponins named as Lebbekanin A, B, C and D.

The bark of *Albizzia lebbek* Benth from U.P. has also been studied by Varshney *et al.*⁵ and reported to contain a saponin of acacic acid.

The present work describes the study of saponin from the wood of this plant.

The crushed defatted wood was extracted with ethanol. The ethanol extract on concentration and usual treatment with different solvents and precipitation in acetone⁶ yielded a light brown substance which gave all the tests for saponin. On TLC in chloroform : methanol : water (65 : 45 : 10) it showed two major spots with traces of impurities. It was therefore purified by chromatography on a column of silica gel using chloroform : methanol : water as eluants and thus a colourless product m.p. 176°–78° was obtained which gave all the tests for saponin and has been named as Lebbekanin E. Besides this sucrose was also isolated and identified.

Lebbekanin E on acid hydrolysis gave acacic acid (27%; 3 β , 16 β , 21 β , trihydroxy-olean-12-ene-18 α H, 28-oic acid)⁷⁻⁹. The hydrolysate after neutralisation and deionisation showed the presence of four sugars identified as glucose, arabinose, xylose, and rhamnose by paper chromatography and TLC.

The sugars after separation by preparative paper chromatography were estimated by colorimetric method using phenol-sulphuric acid¹⁰ and the molar ratio of the sugars, glucose, arabinose, xylose and rhamnose was found to be 4 : 2 : 1 : 1.

Lebbekanin E was unaffected on refluxing with 5% methanolic sodium hydroxide for 4 hr on a water bath and indicated that there is no ester linkage in Lebbekanin E and so the COOH group at C-28 is free.

Lebbekanin E on acetylation gave an acetate. The I.R. spectra of the acetate showed a γ -lactone band at 1770 cm⁻¹ which is absent in the I.R. spectrum of the saponin. This showed that during the acetylation process the 21-OH group and 28-COOH group have lactonised to form a γ -lactone as in case of acacic acid acetylation⁷⁻⁹. This clearly indicated that the 21-OH group and 28-COOH group are free and there is no sugar attachment on these positions. Therefore all the sugar molecules are attached to C-3 OH group and/or C-16 OH group.

On the basis of the data presented above partial structure (I) has been proposed for Lebbekanin E.

Fig. 1. R' and/or R'' = Glucose : Arabinose : Xylose : Rhamnose (4 : 2 : 1 : 1).

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Solid State Interaction between Urea oxalate and Phosphate of Iron and Aluminium

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ACID soils invariably contain iron and aluminium phosphates of low solubility¹. To increase the solubility so as to make these phosphates available to plants, is therefore of considerable interest in soil chemistry. In the present investigation the author attempts to find out the reaction of ferric and aluminium phosphates with urea oxalate on the lines recently reported by Kutty and Murthy² and Pant and Pathak³ in order to determine the conditions for making these phosphates of acid soils available to plants. The work consists of grinding a fixed amount of ferric or aluminium phosphate with varying amounts of urea oxalate so as to determine the particular ratio of the phosphate to urea oxalate necessary for rendering it completely water soluble.

Experimental

Since the exact nature of iron and aluminium phosphates in soils is as yet unknown, the experiments were carried out with laboratory reagent forms, FePO₄·2H₂O and AlPO₄·2H₂O. Urea oxalate was prepared from urea and oxalic acid⁴. It was purified by recrystallization. 1 g mole of ferric phosphate or aluminium phosphate was mixed with varying amounts of urea oxalate and ground in an agate mortar for 1–2 hr under dry conditions. To evaluate available phosphate 1 g of the mixture was leached with 250 ml of water, filtered and the amount of P₂O₅ obtained in the filtrate⁵ was taken as water soluble phosphate. The amount of P₂O₅ soluble in 100 ml of 2% citric acid solution in the residue after leaching with water was taken as the citrate soluble phosphate.